

Manganese (II) Complexes

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In continuation of the previous work on co-ordination compounds of manganese^{1,2}, the syntheses of few manganese(II) chelates are reported in this communication.

The complexes synthesised are of the type $[Mn(AA)X_2]$, where AA=bidentate chelating ligand such as orthophenanthroline, 5-nitro-orthophenanthroline, 2,9-dimethyl-orthophenanthroline, 2-2'-dipyridyl, 8-aminoquinoline etc. and X=Cl or Br.

For the preparation of the complexes an ethanolic solution of manganese (II) salt (1 mole) and the appropriate bidentate ligand (1 mole) were refluxed for half an hour. The resulting crystalline solids were filtered off, washed with absolute alcohol and dried in a desiccator over $CaCl_2$. In some cases there was immediate precipitation of the complexes just after mixing the two solutions.

A few of the representative complexes are included in the Table.

TABLE

Analysis and Physical Properties of the Manganese(II) Complexes.

Compound	Colour	Analytical data						Magnetic moment (B.M.) T=305°K
		Metal		Nitrogen		Halogen		
		Found %	Reqd. %	Found %	Reqd. %	Found %	Reqd. %	
[Mn (o-phen) Br ₂]	Pale yellow	14.2	13.9	7.1	7.0	40.8	40.5	5.86
[Mn (nitro-phen) Cl ₂]	Yellow	15.7	15.6	12.0	11.9	20.4	20.2	5.75
[Mn (dime-phen) Cl ₂]	Pale-yellow	16.6	16.4	8.4	8.3	—	—	5.99
[Mn (dipy) Br ₂]	Pale-yellow	14.5	14.8	7.4	7.5	43.4	43.1	5.85
[Mn (8-Am-Q) Cl ₂]	Pale-yellow	20.1	20.3	10.1	10.3	25.8	26.2	5.90

Where o-phen=orthophenanthroline, nitro-phen=5, nitro orthophenanthroline, dime-phen=2,9-dimethyl-orthophenanthroline, 8-Am-Q=8-amino quinoline.

The ground level of $3d^5$ manganese ion is $6s$ and represents a spherically symmetrical half-filled non-bonding shell, which causes least perturbation to the favoured stereochemistry, tetrahedral or octahedral, the non-bonding shell being $d_{z^2} d_{y^2-x^2}$ or $d_{y^2-x^2} d_{z^2}$ respectively. The tetra-coordinated manganese(II) complexes are usually a rare than the frequently found hexa-coordinated complexes³.

1. A. Syamal, *Ind. J. Chem.*, (in press).
2. A. Syamal *This Journal*, (under publication).
3. N. Goldenberg, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, **36**, 847.

The complexes reported in this study are stable and do not decompose or oxidise even on heating at 120°C for hours. These are non-electrolytes. The room temperature magnetic moments of these complexes were determined by the Gouy method and the values are in the range 5.7—5.9 B.M. (Table), indicative of the presence of five unpaired electrons and the sextate ground state level in these complexes. The expected magnetic moment values of tetrahedral and spin-free octahedral manganese(II) complexes are about 5.9 B.M., while the moment values around 3.88 B.M. have been taken to indicate planar structure. All the complexes studied here have high melting points and poor solubilities in organic solvents—indicative of presumably a polymeric octahedral structure. Mellor and Coryell⁴ have proposed also a similar octahedral structure for manganous dipyridine chloride.

In this connection it may be mentioned that Fanning and Taylor⁵ were unable to prepare the manganous complex of 8-aminoquinoline. This failure is presumably due to their faulty method of preparation in aqueous medium, where generally manganous complexes with nitrogen donors undergo disproportionation.

The visible absorption spectra (both solution and diffuse reflectance) and infra-red spectra of these complexes are in progress. The generality of the synthetic approach is being extended to other metallic elements including cadmium(II) and to a large number of bidentate ligands. Details will be published in due course.

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5. J. C. Fanning and L. T. Taylor, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 2217.